

BIM project progression auditing system: use-case methods Revit plug-in prototype

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Abstract

Projects in the construction industry require input from different stakeholders to create a building information model. This model is a data repository and basis for decision making throughout the project's lifecycle. The final model is typically an aggregate of input from multiple stakeholders and as the project progresses across phases, the model complexity also increases. This is due to the need to take into account more factors as the project becomes more complex.

The benefits that stakeholders can receive from automated data collection systems and tools can help in analysing the efficiency and effectiveness of a process, as well as verifying the accuracy and completeness of a model against established requirements.

A system which facilitates this kind of project auditing, along with actors, use cases, and requirements is helpful in order to maintain a cohesive project. A prototype of a selected use case: tracking project iterations was developed and demonstrated as a proof of concept for the proposed system. Autodesk Revit is a popular Information modelling tool that allows users to extend its functionality through its open API. The prototype was created in Revit API and C programming languages and will be installed as a plugin to extend the Revit default function. The results from the prototype were analysed and discussed in a Business Intelligence dashboard.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/76WDImXfUK0>

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